

DISTRIBUTION OF *IPOMOEA CAPITELLATA* CHOISY VAR. *MULTILOBATA* BHELLUM (CONVOLVULACEAE) IN SOUTHERN WESTERN GHATS, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Occurrence of *Ipomoea capitellata* Choisy var. *multilobata* Bhellum (Convolvulaceae) A new record for Southern Western Ghats, India. A brief description, photograph and relevant notes are provided. During assessment of the diversity of the climbers in the Southern Western Ghats of Tamil Nadu, a specimens belonging to the genus *Ipomoea* were collected. On critical examination of the specimens, it was identified *Ipomoea capitellata* Choisy var. *multilobata* Bhellum a variety so far reported only from Jammu and Kashmir State (Bhellum, 2012) in India. Hence, the presence reported forms a new distributional record for Southern Western Ghats in India.

Key words : *Ipomoea capitellata* var. *multilobata*, New Distributional Record, Southern Western Ghats.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Ipomoea* L. comprising about 500 species is distributed throughout the tropics of the Old and New World (Austin & Huaman, 1996). Recently *Ipomoea mombassana* Vatke, *Ipomoea parasitica* (Kunth) G. Don and *Ipomoea ochracea* (Lindl.) G. Don was reported from India (Biju, 2002; Biju *et al.*, 1998; Shimpale *et al.*, 2012). In India, it is represented by about 56 species (Biju, 1997 and Kottai muthu, 2013).

During assessment of the diversity of the climbers in the Southern Western Ghats of Tamil Nadu, a specimens belonging to the genus *Ipomoea* were collected. On critical examination of the specimens, it was identified *Ipomoea capitellata* Choisy var. *multilobata* Bhellum a variety so far reported only from Jammu and Kashmir State (Bhellum, 2012) in India. Hence,

the presence reported forms a new distributional record for Southern Western Ghats in India. Therefore it is reported here with brief description, nomenclature, photograph and other relevant details for easy identification of the taxa in the field.

Ipomoea capitellata Choisy var. *multilobata* Bhellum in *J. Res. Pl. Sci.* 1: 060-062. 2012. (Figure-1 & 2.)

Brief Description:

Annual, stem straggling or twining with long spreading hairs; leaves 3.8-10 cm long usually a few to multilobed, lobes ovate, acute or acuminate, narrowed at the base, hirsute on both the surfaces; petiole 3.8-7.5 cm long, very hairy; flowers sessile, 3 or more in a head; peduncle 2.5- 7.5 cm long, hairy; outer bracts nearly 2.5 cm, inner ones 1cm long, all ovate-oblong, sub-obtuse, hairy; sepals 8- 13 mm long, densely hairy, ciliate with long stiff hairs; outer sepals

broader than the inner ovate-lanceolate, the inner three linear-oblong, acute; corolla ca ca 3 cm long tubular, campanulate, white or pale-pink; capsule 6 mm across, globose, glabrous, papery, concealed in the calyx; seeds 5 mm long, grey, pubescent.

Flowering & Fruiting: August- October

Distribution in India: INDIA: Jammu and Kashmir State. Tamil Nadu: Coimbatore District -Anamalai, Maruthamalai and Anaikatty hills of the Southern Western Ghats.

Habitat:

A common twiner along hedges of the moist evergreen and deciduous forests. The species can be easily recognized by its setose sepals and hairy capsules.

Specimens examined:

Tamil Nadu; Anamalai, Maruthamalai and Anaikatty hills of the Southern Western Ghats.

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The species is found growing abundantly in its new habitat in Southern western Ghats and therefore, it is likely that it may soon become naturalized.

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Figure.1&2: *Ipomoea capitellata* Choisy var. *multilobata* Bhellum: A). Habit, B). Leaf, C). Calyx, D) Corolla, E) Capsule, F) Seed

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